

5 Case Studies Need Question's Answers

Case 1: Is Daylight Saving time Efficient?

Executive Summary

This case is about the daylight saving time and the focus is on its effectiveness, the case governs around the overall efficiency or inefficiency of U.S economy during the daylight saving time. This case identifies that switching to the daylight saving time each year results in less efficient economy as compared to the economic condition during the standard time in U.S.

Answer 1: Inefficiency basically means that scarce or limited resources are not optimally utilized; this case is about the electricity resources it is stated that during the daylight saving time these resources are more used rather than the anticipated less consumption. Because switching to daylight saving time demands more electricity consumption as compared to standard time. Indiana example is given in this case that air conditioner are used more to maintain a low temperature. So we can say that because of inefficiency, same resources are utilized and lesser output is generated (Shleifer & Summers, 1990).

Answer 2: It is possible because remaining on the daylight saving time it depends upon us, the contentions about its conceivable profits and disadvantages come up twice consistently, and however it does certainly cause a lot of hindrance. So the better alternative would be to use natural daylight and making most of it. There is a time difference in different seasons as well. The best alternatives could be the use of solar energy, and other resources and utilizing the daylight to the maximum extent despite of switching in every year, as switching to daylight saving time is not that much efficient for the economy as it is perceived.

Case 2: Pricing the iPad: learning lesson from the iPhone

Executive Summary

This case is about the pricing strategies of Apple Inc. it discuss the scenario when Apple anticipated an inelastic demand of iPhone and set a higher price of its product to get more revenue but the revenue the received was only increased when the smart phone demand declined in 2007-2008. Then many people's anticipated that Apple will launch iPad with higher price but they launched it on half of anticipated price around \$499 they thought that the demand will be elastic and they will generate more revenues.

Answer 1: Price elasticity of demand measures the percentage change in quantity demanded of a good as a variation in the price of this asset. In this Apple case if the elasticity of demand is more or equivalent to 1 then this shows that the percent change in amount is extraordinary than the percent change in value, then the curve will be generally flat and elastic: little value changes will have vast consequences for demand. On the off chance that the elasticity of the demand curve is below 1, significance the percent change in amount is less than the percent change in value, then the curve will be steep and inelastic: it will take a huge change in cost to influence demand (Rodrik, 2011).

Answer 2: The price elasticity of demand of Apple product is greater than the price elasticity of market demand because Apple anticipated that the demand will be elastic and no matter if they kept the price lower they will generate higher revenue because they will be selling more products, and that is the reason that Apple sets the price of its product lower because they want the demand to be elastic.

Case 3: Adjusting To a Lower Market Clearing Price of Solar Cells

Executive Summary

This case is about the Q-Cells, company that is producing the largest volume of solar cells microchips that are utilized in solar power system worldwide. This case focuses on the substantial drop down of market clearing prices. The prices have declined greatly and one watt of electrical power is now of \$2 whereas it was at \$4 in 2008. The company management is focusing on different retrenchment and downsizing strategies and is running cost saving strategy, that is why the company has cut down the staff by 10 percent and other expansions have also been stopped since a better market situation.

Answer 1: the solar industry has experienced a decrease in quantity supplied around 50 percent of the supply has been dropped and the industry is facing a substantial price fall. The prices have decreased from \$4 to \$2 today as compared to 2008.

Answer 2: A change in the quantity supplied to market occurs as a response to change or variation in the price and it can be observed as movement along the supply curve. As in this case a huge amount of price fall has been observed this has resulted in the downsizing and no future expansions in the company. This condition will prevail unless the market clearing price will recover otherwise the company will go for the option of downsizing further and also for the production of even few solar cells.

Case 4: “Cash for Clunkers”- Subsidies and the market for “Liquid Glass”

Executive Summary

This case is about the use of sodium-silicate chemical solution that is known as liquid glass this solution is used to prevent leaks in engine gaskets which might result in cylinder or engine blocks. Now the prices have risen from \$2.50 to \$3.50 per quart, the reason behind this

rise is that another use of this solution has been found which made it extremely helpful for mechanics to repair the engines of gas-guzzling vehicles. Another reason behind the price hike was the substantial increase in demand for liquid glass (Rodrik, 2011).

Answer 1: This program which was running under the federal government known as “Cash for Clunkers” resulted in a shift in the market demand curve for liquid glass, as after that program the demand increases and that is the reasons that many solution companies started to produce on order and that chemical solution was utilized for the necessary purpose. The prices of the chemical solution was greatly increased because of the rise in the demand of the solution as more need were created for the solution after the federal government “Cash for Clunkers” program according to which energy inefficient vehicles can be traded in with energy efficient vehicles and subsidies can be received (Shleifer & Summers, 1990).

Answer 2: The “Cash for Clunker” program generated a temporary shift in the market supply curve of the liquid glass and the reason behind this was that the demand was increased for the liquid glass because of the federal government program and also because of its use in the engine of the old vehicles as it was necessary for the repairing purpose (Shleifer & Summers, 1990).

Case 5: Questioning China’s Real GDP Statistics

Executive Summary

Initially the case discusses the increase in China’s GDP the government claims that their GDP or Gross Domestic product increase by 4% whereas many economists believe that it only increase by 1.5 %. Some Economist believes that many other sectors might have contributed to the increase in GDP of china despite of some performance downfall in Steel and Aluminum industry.

Answer 1: Many observers have different assumption about the true GDP statistics some think that the countries show inaccurate or wrongly attributed statistics. Like in this case many believe that the GDP is at different percentage. Some time the governments might show false statistics to show the positive status of the economic condition of their country, if the private companies tabulates the data the chances for accurate data collection would be much more as they will be doing it without any influence and they will be mentioning the performance of different sectors that the government may want to hide for some time because of its ongoing projects. GDP can be calculated in three different ways: by the supply side, from the demand side or the optical performance. GDP should not vary according to the calculation method used. The three different GDP calculation methods shall always bear the same result (Shleifer & Summers, 1990).

Answer 2: The nonprofit organizations will be having no direct interest in any business and will new businesses will not be giving any sort of direct support to the nonprofit organizations so it could be one of the reason for that and that is why the US government wants to leave the decisions of business expansion and contraction on a nonprofit organization so as to show that government has no influence in any such activity.

References

Shleifer, A., & Summers, L. H. (1990). THE QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*.

Rodrik, D. (2011). Comments on “New Structural Economics” by Justin Yifu Lin. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 26(2), 227-229.